

AVIAN AVULAVIRUS 1 OUTBREAKS IN BULGARIA DURING 2016 AND 2017

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ABSTRACT

Newcastle disease is one of the most important and highly contagious disease for poultry. The causative agent Avian avulavirus 1 belongs to genus Avulavirus, Family Paramyxoviridae, order Mononegavirales. There are two evolutionary related groups AAvV-1 – class I and class II. The classification is based on complete genome analysis. Class I and class II being further divided in genotypes. However, the isolation and identification of novel avulaviruses of varying pathogenicity and genotypes from a wide range of hosts suggests a continuous virus evolution with subsequent implications for disease spread. Subsequent to evolution, the emergence of novel genotypes and sub-genotypes are now increasing over a period of time. Despite the introduction of a broad vaccination program in industrial poultry farms in Bulgaria, the birds in the backyard farms have not been vaccinated and the disease has become endemic. Almost every year there is at least one outbreak in poultry or wild birds. The earlier AAvV-1 isolates, from 1959 to 1998, belong to many different genetic lines: 2, 3b, 3c, 4 and 5b. The last AAvV-1 isolates (from 2004 to 2013) from chickens belong to genetic line 5d and wild bird isolates belongs to 1, 2, 4b and 6. The first appearance of genetic line 5a is in the beginning of 2013. All this necessitates in-depth studies of AAvV-1 in the population of both wild and synanthropic birds and vaccinated hens. This study was conducted to ascertain the genetics of the circulating AAvV-1 that causes disease outbreaks in 2016 and 2017.

Key words: Avian avulavirus-1, rRT-PCR, Phylogenetic analysis, Bulgaria, diagnosis.

Introduction

Newcastle disease (ND), caused by virulent Avian avulavirus 1 (AAvV 1), is a highly contagious disease, one of the most important in commercial poultry industry which leads to serious economic losses to the poultry trade worldwide (Haji-Abdolvahab et al., 2019). According to the new classification the Newcastle disease virus (NDV) or AAvV 1 belong to the genus Orthoavulavirus within the family Paramyxoviridae (Amarasinghe et al., 2019). The genome is single stranded RNA with negative sense composed by either 15186, 15192 or 15198 nucleotides which codes several proteins: nucleocapsid (N), phosphoprotein (P), matrix (M), fusion (F), haemagglutinin-neuraminidase (HN) and large polymerase (L) protein in the order 3'-NP-P/V/W-M-F-HN-L-5' (Kolakovsky et al., 2005).

The virulence of the various AAvV-1 varies considerably, and accordingly the clinical symptoms range from no to severe clinical signs, respiratory distress, or neurological signs and death (Alexander, 1997; Alexander, 1998). Various methods have been developed to classify the AAvV-1 isolates according to their virulence. Historically, AAvV-1 isolates have been pathotyped into four groups based on their clinical presentation: asymptomatic (non-virulent); lentogenic - usually low virulent; mesogenic - with respiratory or neurological clinical presentation; and velogenic (viscerotropic or neurotropic) - with severe clinical signs and often with lethal outcome (Alexander et al., 2012). The currently internationally recognized method for classifying the virulence of AAvV-1 strains is the intracerebral pathogenic index (ICPI), which can be further supported by sequencing of the F protein cleavage site (Herczeg et al., 1999). Strains with an ICPI of 0.7 to 1.5 are considered

mesogenic, while those with an ICPI > 1.5 are velogenic (Alexander, 1997). The F protein cleavage site has been found to be the major molecular determinant of AAvV-1 virulence. Strains with a F protein cleavage site with at least 3 arginine or lysine residues between positions 113 and 116 and a phenylalanine residue at position 117 are considered velogenic (Herczeg et al., 1999).

There are two evolutionarily related groups AAvV-1- class I and class II. The classification is based on a complete genomic analysis (Czeglédi et al., 2006). Class I and class II are further divided into genotypes (Aldous, 2003). Class I strains have a genomic size of 15,198 nt and are most commonly isolated from waterfowl and coastal birds (Czeglédi et al., 2006; Miller et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2007). Class II strains have genomic sizes of 15,186 nt and are found in many species of wild and domestic birds, and this class contains some of the more virulent genotypes (Miller et al., 2009). Within class two, there is a third group with a genome length of 15,192 nt. Some authors (Herczeg et al., 1999; Herczeg et al., 2001; Lomniczi et al., 1998) divide the isolates into eight genetic lines (I-VIII), with several sub-lines included in them. Other authors (Aldous et al., 2003) divide them into six genetic lines (1-6), with lines 3 and 4 including 4 sublines (a-d), and line 5 including 5 sublines (a-e). Therefore, lines 1, 2, 4 and 5 correspond to the previously defined lines I, II, VI and VII, with the equivalent sub-lines, and gene groups III, IV, V and VIII correspond to sub-lines 3a to 3d. Line 6 represents a new genogroup. Although the AAvV-1 isolates placed in groups 1–5 (respectively I-VIII) are genetically similar, the viruses placed in gene group 6 (Aldous et al., 2003), and later in class I (Czeglédi et al., 2006) are very different from all other AAvV-1 isolates. However, the isolation and identification of novel avulaviruses of varying pathogenicity and genotypes from a wide range of hosts (Ramey et al., 2013; Shabbir et al., 2016; Brown & Bevins, 2017; Dodovski et al., 2017; Qiu et al., 2017; El Naggat et al., 2018; Aziz-ul-Rahman et al., 2018) suggests a continuous virus evolution with subsequent implications for disease spread (Miller et al., 2015; Fan et al., 2017). Subsequent to evolution, the emergence of novel genotypes and sub-genotypes are now increasing over a period of time (Dimitrov et al., 2019a). The phylogenetic analysis revealed the circulation of 21 genotypes globally and, among these, genotype VI and VII viruses are predominantly circulating and causing several outbreaks in developing countries (Liang et al., 2002; Abolnik et al., 2018; Dimitrov et al., 2019b).

Despite the introduction of a broad vaccination program in industrial poultry farms in Bulgaria, the birds in the backyard farms have not been vaccinated and the disease has become endemic. Almost every year there is at least one outbreak in poultry or wild birds. The earlier AAvV-1 isolates, from 1959 to 1998, belong to many different genetic lines: 2, 3b, 3c, 4 and 5b. The last AAvV-1 isolates (from 2004 to 2013) from chickens belong to genetic line 5d and wild bird isolates belongs to 1, 2, 4b and 6. The first appearance of genetic line 5a is in the beginning of 2013.

Materials and methods

1. Materials

1.1. Viruses

In the present study referent strain Ulster 2C, IZV, Italy have been used.

1.2. Monospecific serum for haemagglutination inhibition test

Serum NDV Ulster 2C (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie, Italy)

Specific sera for Avian influenza subtypes H5N2, H7N3 and H9N2 (IZSVE, Italy).

1.3. Biological systems

As a biological system for virus isolation 9 to 11 days old embrionated chicken eggs were used, derived from flocks free of the Newcastle disease.

During the necropsy, trachea and intestines from birds showing specific clinical signs for new-castle disease were collected and were used as a material for virus isolation.

2. Methods

2.1. Virus isolation and identification

Organs from each birds were pooled, homogenized, and the samples were centrifuged at 800g for 10 minutes at 4°C. Inoculation into the allantoic cavity of three 9 to 11-day-old embryonated chicken eggs (ECE) was then performed using 200µl of supernatant from each organ sample. The infected embryos were incubated at 37°C and checked daily for embryo death.

2.2. RNA extraction.

Viral RNA from the source samples was extracted with two different commercial extraction kits (QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit – QIAGEN and High Pure RNA Isolation Kit - Roche), according to the manufacturer's protocols.

2.3. Reverse transcriptional polymerase chain reaction.

QIAGEN One-Step RT-PCR Kit-QIAGEN with Central Reference Laboratory protocols – EURLWeybridge, UK was used to perform the reaction to detect M and F genes from the genome of the AAvV-1. The sequences of the specific primers and probe are listed in table. 1. The thermal regime was as follows: 50°C for 30 min, 95°C for 15 min, followed by 40 cycles at 95°C for 10 sec and 52°C for 45 sec.

Table 1: Sequences of all used primers and probes.

Primers and probes	Sequences
M+4100	5'-AGTGATGTGCTCGGACCTTC-3'
M+4169	5'-[FAM]TTCTCTAGCAGTGGGACAGCCTGC[TAMRA]-3'
M-4220	5'-CCTGAGGAGAGGCATTTGCTA-3'
F+4839	5'-TCCGGAGGATACAAGGGTCT-3'
F+4894 (VFP-1)	5'-[FAM]AAGCGTTTCTGTCTCCTTCCTCCA[TAMRA]-3'
F-4939	5'-AGCTGTTGCAACCCCAAG-3'

2.4. Sequencing.

Sequencing and molecular analysis were performed at the Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA), UK.

Results

During 2016 and 2017 we isolated 6 viruses from 5 administrative regions of Bulgaria: disrict Kardzhali – Nenkovo and Rudina villages; disrict Haskovo – Balkan village; disrict Montana – Lom; disrict Vidin – Gomotarsi village and disrict Smolyan – Rudozem (table 2).

Table 2: AAV-1 outbreaks data in Bulgaria during 2016–2017.

Outbreak	Isolation date	Affected Species	Susceptible	Affected	Died	Destroyed
Nenkovo	04-02-2016	Laying Hens	301	61	61	240
Rudina	22-02-2016	Laying Hens	676	15	15	661
Balkan	09-03-2016	Laying Hens	54	14	15	54
Lom	26-10-2016	Laying Hens /Geese	28/3	19/0	19/0	9/3
Gomotarzi	20-12-2016	Laying Hens	67	44	44	13
Rudozem	17-03-2017	Laying Hens	60	6	6	138

The most commonly reported clinical symptoms by farmers were: Labored breathing, depression, muscle tremor, shaking of the head, green watery diarrhea.

The Necropsy revealed Anemic and dehydrated carcasses and also petechial haemorrhages on the glandular stomach mucosa. Changes were observed and in the respiratory system, mainly in the trachea, ranging from increased exudation to multiple petechial hemorrhages.

All samples were first tested by the rRT-PCR method to detect M- and F-genes. Ct values are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: rRT_PCR results, Ct values for M and F genes.

Outbreaks	Cts, M gene (Wise et al, 2004)		Cts, F gene (Wise et al, 2004)	
	Trachea	Intestine	Trachea	Intestine
Nenkovo	21.10	19.26	33.40	32.53
Rudina	25.12	27.32	37.69	39.22
Balkan	26.91	24.56	35.50	38.00
Lom	21.49	25.31	25.34	31.79
Gomotarzi	25.16	24.32	27.60	32.02
Rudozem	21.16	23.95	26.88	30.78

After obtaining a positive result for the M- and F-genes of AAV-1, we proceeded to isolate the virus in chicken embryos. The viruses killed the embryos by the 48th hour. The collected allantoic fluids were tested for haemagglutination activity. All isolates showed a positive haemagglutination reaction. In a haemagglutination inhibition reaction (HI), the same samples showed positive results when bound to Ulster 2C antiserum, while the results were negative for Influenza A

Further pathotyping was performed in EURL Weybridge. The results of the direct nucleotide sequencing of the gene encoding the F-protein and the determination of the amino acid sequence at the cleavage site are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Results from Phylogenetic analysis of the isolated viruses during studied period.

Outbreak	AAV-1 sequence in cleavage site of the F protein	Phylogenetic analysis	Genotype
Nenkovo	RRQKRF	99,7% RO15-041619CK, 99,5% RO15-054070CK	5d
Rudina	RRQKRF	99,7% CY13-0214151CK,	5a
Balkan	RRQKRF	99,5% TR 12-015958CK,	5d
Lom	RRQKRF	99,2% BG AV-13-002543CK	5d

The sequences of Bulgarian AAvV-1 isolates from 2016 and 2017 were compared with sequences of viruses detected in Bulgaria in 2007, 2009, 1995, 1996, as well as with the sequences of virus isolates from the neighboring countries: Romania, Turkey and Greece detected in 2015–2016.

Discussion

The first outbreak of Newcastle disease in Bulgaria was reported in 1943 close to airport occupied by the German military, from where the disease spread rapidly. In 1951 the Bulgarian veterinary authorities managed to control the disease by vaccinations. In the late 50s of the twentieth century, outbreak of the disease were reported again, and since then every year outbreaks are reported and the disease became endemic (Hadjiev, G., 1973). In a retrospective review of outbreaks over the past 20 years, the most frequently affected areas are in northern Bulgaria along the Danube River and the bordering areas close to Turkey and Greece. Cases of AAvV-1 in wild birds are in most frequent in regions where migratory birds congregate-the Black Sea coast (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Newcastle disease affected provinces and municipalities during 2016 and 2017.

Reported outbreaks Newcastle disease in 2016–2017 were again in Northern and Southern Bulgaria. In three out of six outbreaks, the isolated viruses belong to genotype 5d, one belong to 5a, the other two have not been identified. It was very interesting that the identified genotypes involved in the first and second outbreaks, although located only 60 km from each other, were different genetic lines. On 4.02.2016 the disease has been reported again in the Nenkovovo village, Kardzhali municipality, caused by a virus belonging to genotype 5d. Twenty days later, in the same region in the village of Rudina, the AAvV-1 reappeared, but this time it was 5a genotype. On March 9, 2016, in the neighboring district of Haskovo in the Balkan village, located 60 km from the village of Nenkovovo and 20 km from the Rudina village, a virus belonging to genotype 5d appeared.

In the phylogenetic analysis of the isolates it was found that those belonging to the genetic line 5d are 99.7% close to the Romanian isolate from 2015, and are 99.5% identical. The virus from the

village of Rudina is 99.7% similarities with virus isolated in 2013 in Cyprus; 99.5% to virus isolated in Turkey during 2012, and 99.25% to Bulgarian isolate from the village of Zvinitsa, district Kardzhali, but detected during 2013. In previous studies by other authors (Dimitrov et al., 2016) of the isolate from the village of Zvinitsa, close relationship of this virus with isolates from Libya, Pakistan and Israel is reported. The ancestor of all these viruses is thought to have originated in Indonesia, where Newcastle disease first appeared.

During 10 years period from 2007 to 2017 in Europe, genotype 5d has been found in Bulgaria, Hungary, Switzerland, Turkey, Greece and Romania. This shows that the virus is spreading in two directions: east-west and north-south. Whether it is about individual introductions in these countries are related to the migration of wild birds or illegal trade, can not be concluded. According to some authors (DelesaDamena et al., 2016), wild pigeons play an important role in the epidemiology of the disease. We do not have such evidence to support this thesis, because during the period of our analysis we did not study wild pigeons, but we cannot reject it. Particular attention should be paid to the supervision of synanthropic and migratory birds.

There are authors (Alexander et al. 1999) who support the theory that vaccinated hens can secrete a velogenic viruses. If those viruses enters into unvaccinated herd and infect them, it can cause the disease.

All this necessitates in-depth studies of AA_vV-1 in the population of both wild and synanthropic birds and vaccinated hens.

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References

1. Hadzhiev G. (1973). „*Prouchvania varhu nqkoi svoistva na shtamovete na virusa na psevdochumata po pticite, izolirani v Bulgaria*“. Disertacionen trud za prisujdane na obrazovatelna I nauchna stepen “doctor”, NDRIVMI, Sofia. pp. 1–214.
2. Aldous E.W., Mynn J.K., Banks J., Alexander D.J. (2003). *A molecular epidemiological study of avian paramyxovirus type 1 (Newcastle disease virus) isolates by phylogenetic analysis of a partial nucleotide sequence of the fusion protein gene*. Avian Pathol. 32(3), 239–56.
3. Alexander, D. J., (1997). *Newcastle disease and other Paramyxoviridae infections*. In B. W. Calnek, H. J. Barnes, C. W. Beard, L. McDougald, and J. Y. M. Saif (ed.), *Diseases of poultry*, 10th ed. Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa. pp. 541–569.
4. Alexander, D. J. (1998). Newcastle disease virus and other avian paramyxoviruses. In D. E. Swayne, J. R. Glisson, M. W. Jackwood, J. E. Pearson, and W. M. Reed (ed.), *A laboratory manual for the isolation and identification of avian pathogens*, 4th ed. American Association of Avian Pathologists, Kennett Square, Pa. pp. 156–168.
5. Alexander, D. J., Manvell R. J., Banks J., Collins M.S., Parsons G., Cox B., Frost K.M., Speidel E.C., Ashman S., Aldous E.W. (1999). *Experimental assessment of the pathogenicity of the Newcastle disease viruses from outbreaks in Great Britain in 1997 for chickens and turkeys, and the protection afforded by vaccination*. Avian Pathology, 28, 501–512.
6. Czeglédi, A., Ujvári D., Somogyi E., Wehmann E., Werner O., Lomniczi B. (2006). Third genome size category of avian paramyxovirus serotype 1 (Newcastle disease virus) and evolutionary implications. Virus Res.120 (1–2), 36–48.

7. Damena D., Fusaro A., Sombo M., Belaineh R., Heidari A., Kebede A., Kidane M., Chaka H., (2016). Characterization of Newcastle disease virus isolates obtained from outbreak cases in commercial chickens and wild pigeons in Ethiopia. *Springer Plus*. 5, 476.
8. Dimitrov K. M., Ramey A. M., Qiu X., Bahl J., Afonso C. L., (2016). *Temporal, geographic, and host distribution of avian paramyxovirus 1 (Newcastle disease virus)*. *Infect. Genet. Evol.* 39, 22–34.
9. Herczeg J., Wehmann E., Bragg R. R., Travassos Dias P. M., Hadjiev G., Werner O., Lomniczi B. (1999). *Two novel genetic groups (VIIb and VIII) responsible for recent Newcastle disease outbreaks in Southern Africa, one (VIIb) of which reached Southern Europe*. *Arch. Virol.* 144, 2087–2099.
10. Herczeg J., Pascucci S., Massi P., Luini M., Selli L., Capua I., Lomniczi B. (2001). *A longitudinal study of velogenic Newcastle disease virus genotypes isolated in Italy between 1960 and 2000*. *Avian Pathology*, 30, 163–168.
11. International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV). <https://talk.ictvonline.org/taxonomy/>
12. Kim L. M., King D. J., Curry P. E., Suarez D. L., Swayne D. E., Stallknecht D. E., Slemmons R. D., Pedersen J. C., Senne D. A., Winker K., Afonso C. L. (2007). *Phylogenetic diversity among low-virulence newcastle disease viruses from waterfowl and shorebirds and comparison of genotype distributions to those of poultry-origin isolates*. *J Virol.* 81(22), 12641–53.
13. Lomniczi B., Wehmann E., Herczeg J., Ballagi-Pordany A., Kaleta E. F., Werner O., Meulemans D., Jorgensen P. H., Mante A. P., Gielkens A. L. J., Damoser J. (1998). *Newcastle disease outbreaks in recent years in Western Europe were caused by an old (VI) and a novel genotype (VII)*. *Archives of Virology*, 143, 49–64.
14. Wise M. G., Suarez D. L., Seal B. S., Pedersen J. C., Senne D. A., King D. J., Kapczynski D. R., Spackman E. (2004). *Development of a Real-Time Reverse-Transcription PCR for Detection of Newcastle Disease Virus RNA in Clinical Samples*. *J Clin Microbiol.*42(1), 329–338.
15. Miller P. J., Kim L. M., Ip H. S., Afonso C. L. (2009). *Evolutionary dynamics of Newcastle disease virus*. *Virology*.15, 391(1), 64–72.
16. OIE Manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals 2016, chapter 2.3.1.14. <http://www.oie.int/international-standard-setting/terrestrial-manual/>.
17. Courtney S. C., Susta L., Gomez D., Hines N. L., Pedersen J. C., Brown C. C., Miller P. J., Afonso C. L. (2013). *Highly Divergent Virulent Isolates of Newcastle Disease Virus from the Dominican Republic Are Members of a New Genotype That May Have Evolved Unnoticed for Over 2 Decades*. *J Clin Microbiol.*51(2), 508–517.
18. Haji-Abdolvahab H., Ghalyanchilangeroudi A., Bahonar A., Ghafouri S.A., Marandi M.V., Mehrabadi M.H.F., Tehrani F. (2019). *Prevalence of avian influenza, Newcastle disease, and infectious bronchitis viruses in broiler flocks infected with multifactorial respiratory diseases in Iran, 2015–2016*. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 51, 689–695. doi: 10.1007/s11250-018-1743-z.
19. Kolakofsky D., Roux L., Garcin D., Ruigrok R.W. (2005). *Paramyxovirus mRNA editing, the 'rule of six' and error catastrophe: a hypothesis*. *Journal of General Virology*, 86, 1869–1877. doi: 10.1099/vir.0.80986-0.
20. Alexander D.J., Aldous E.W., Fuller C.M. (2012). *The long view: a selective review of 40 years of Newcastle disease research*. *Avian Pathology*, 41, 329–335. doi: 10.1080/03079457.2012.697991
21. Ramey A.M., Reeves A.B., Ogawa H., Ip H.S., Imai K., Bui V.N., Yamaguchi E., Silko N.Y., Afonso, C.L. (2013). *Genetic diversity and mutation of avian paramyxovirus serotype 1 (Newcastle disease virus) in wild birds and evidence for intercontinental spread*. *Archives of Virology*, 158, 2495–2503. doi: 10.1007/s00705-013-1761-0.

22. Shabbir M.Z., Akhtar S., Tang Y., Yaqub T., Ahmad A., Mustafa G., Alam M.A., Santhakumar D., Nair V. (2016). *Infectivity of wild bird origin avian Paramyxovirus serotype 1 and vaccine effectiveness in chickens*. Journal of General Virology, 97, 3161–3173. doi: 10.1099/jgv.0.000618.
23. Brown V.R., Bevins S.N. (2017). *A review of virulent Newcastle disease viruses in the United States and the role of wild birds in viral persistence and spread*. Veterinary Research, 48, 68. doi: 10.1186/s13567-017-0475-9.
24. Dodovski A., Cvetkovikj I., Krstevski K., Naletoski I., Savić V. (2017). *Characterization and epidemiology of pigeon paramyxovirus type-1 viruses (PPMV-1) isolated in Macedonia*. Avian Diseases, 61, 146–152. doi: 10.1637/11517-101816-Reg.1.
25. Qiu X., Meng C., Zhan Y., Yu S., Li S., Ren T., Yuan W., Xu S., Sun Y., Tan L., Song C. (2017). *Phylogenetic, antigenic and biological characterization of pigeon paramyxovirus type 1 circulating in China*. Virology Journal, 14, 186. doi: 10.1186/s12985-017-0857-7.
26. El Naggar R.F., Rohaim M.A., Bazid A.H., Ahmed K.A., Hussein H.A., Munir M. (2018). *Biological characterization of wild-bird-origin avian avulavirus 1 and efficacy of currently applied vaccines against potential infection in commercial poultry*. Archives of Virology, 163, 2743–2755. doi: 10.1007/s00705-018-3916-5.
27. Aziz-ul-Rahman, Munir M., Shabbir M.Z. (2018). *Comparative evolutionary and phylogenomic analysis of avian avulaviruses 1–20*. Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, 127, 931–951. doi: 10.1016/j.ympev.2018.06.040.
28. Miller P.J., Haddas R., Simanov L., Lublin A., Rehmani S.F., Wajid A., Bibi T., Khan T.A., Yaqub T., Setiyaningsih S., Afonso C.L. (2015). *Identification of new sub-genotypes of virulent Newcastle disease virus with potential panzootic features*. Infection, Genetics and Evolution, 29, 216–229. doi: 10.1016/j.meegid.2014.10.032.
29. Fan W., Wang Y., Wang S., Cheng Z., Guo H., Zhao X., Liu J. (2017). *Virulence in Newcastle disease virus: a genotyping and molecular evolution spectrum perspective*. Research in Veterinary Science, 111, 49–54. doi: 10.1016/j.rvsc.2016.12.001.
30. Dimitrov K.M., Abolnik C., Afonso C.L., Albina E., Bahl J., Berg M., Briand F.X., Brown I.H., Choi K.S., Chvala I., Diel D.G. (2019a). *Updated unified phylogenetic classification system and revised nomenclature for Newcastle disease virus*. Infection, Genetics and Evolution, 74: 103917. doi: 10.1016/j.meegid.2019.103917.
31. Liang R., Cao D.J., Li J.Q., Chen J., Guo X., Zhuang F.F., Duan M.X. (2002). *Newcastle disease outbreaks in western China were caused by the genotypes VIIa and VIII*. Veterinary Microbiology, 87, 193–203. doi: 10.1016/S0378-1135(02)00050-0.
32. Abolnik C., Mubamba C., Wandrag D.B., Horner R., Gummow B., Dautu G., Bisschop S.P. (2018). *Tracing the origins of genotype VII h Newcastle disease in Southern Africa*. Transboundary and Emerging Diseases, 65, e393–e403. doi: 10.1111/tbed.12771.
33. Dimitrov K.M., Ferreira H.L., Pantin-Jackwood M.J., Taylor T.L., Goraichuk I.V., Crossley B.M., Killian M.L., Bergeson N.H., Torchetti M.K., Afonso C.L., Suarez D.L. (2019b). *Pathogenicity and transmission of virulent Newcastle disease virus from the 2018–2019 California outbreak and related viruses in young and adult chickens*. Virology, 531, 203–218. doi: 10.1016/j.virol.2019.03.010.
34. Amarasinghe G.K., Ayllón M.A., Bào Y., Basler C.F., Bavari S., Blasdel K.R., Briese T., Brown P.A., Bukreyev A., Balkema-Buschmann A., Buchholz U.J. (2019). *Taxonomy of the order Mononegavirales: update 2019*. Archives of Virology, 164, 1967–1980. doi: 10.1007/s00705-019-04247-4.